

OPEN RESEARCH CHALLENGES IN HEALTH CARE INTERNET OF FORENSICS (H-IoF)

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Abstract:

The human race has to acquaint with the up-to-date developments in order to be competent enough to regulate technology and to embrace the evolving healthcare technologies in order to stay pertinent in the imminent years. The health care data generated by the IoMT in the healthcare sector, poses many hurdles in managing them as they are of different types, voluminous, and are generated at high speed, making it difficult to store in local machines. IoMT is a sub branch of IoT and it deals with the medical devices and health care related crimes and it demands the examination of the relevant devices; besides the other research challenges like security, privacy etc., In order to settle the dispute among the parties legally, after the occurrence of a data breach event; a digital forensics mechanism has to be devised proactively in order to regulate and renovates the chain of events by examining the physical evidence and electronic data; apply analytical techniques to detect, excerpt, preserve, and analyze digital information; Post-Mortem investigation; case-centered; time-restricted process; Forensics Readiness; stipulate the judicial area and legal characteristics in service legal agreements concerning the forensics issues. This paper work presents a rationalized review of the Healthcare Internet of Things (H-IoT), rationale for the study of IoMT forensics, applications, various open research challenges in Healthcare Internet of Forensics (H-IoF). Healthcare Internet of Forensics or IoMT forensics, an umbrella term, encasing issues of IoMT and Digital Forensics, may support in investigating IoMT ecosystems and quickly respond to and report IoMT security incidents. This study provokes the necessity for Healthcare Internet of Forensics. Moreover, this study also reveals the need for immediate research that are capable enough to be rendered as solutions. Last but not the least, this paper provides an insight into the latest IoMT forensics research trends, which will prove beneficial in the development of Digital forensic investigation process.

Key Words: attack attribution, dynamic, evidence presentation, identification, integrated into information network, Internet of Things (IoT), interoperable communication protocols, Medical Internet of Things, preservation, Self-Adapting, Self-Configuring, Unique Identity.

1. Internet of Things:

Recent 2020 report given by the World Bank and WHO, states that approximately half of the world population can't afford or even access to elementary Health Care services. The report further expresses the prevalent incongruity in the availability and affordability of Health Care services even in the industrialized world. The magical solution to this scenario is Internet of Things.

“Internet of Things (IoT)” term was first used by Kevin Ashton in 1999, a pioneer of British technology. Kevin Ashton, defines Internet of Things as, “the system of physical objects in the world that connect to the internet via a sensor”. IoT characterizes the intersperse of physical objects (“things”) over public or private Internet Protocol networks. The physical objects can be anything like devices, machines, things, people.

Hu, Xie, and Shen (2013) defined the term “Medical Internet of Things” as “a kind of technology that embeds wireless sensors in medical equipment, combines with the internet and integrates with hospitals, patients and medical equipment to promote the new development of modern medical model” (p. 2054).

Medical IoT is used to avoid, identify and comprehend diseases, reduce medical expenses, and detect factors that hinder the overall health status to intensify the quality of life. Smart IoT services will endure to transfigure how healthcare is distributed and how we regulate our health [Karakra A, et al., (2018), Bryant N, et al., (2017), Laaki H, et al., (2019), Liu Y, et al., (2019)].

1.1 Characteristics of Internet of Things (IoT):

The many characteristics of IoT have spiraled its utilities in many domains and spheres. From across various literatures one can compile the list of all possible characteristics of IoT as Dynamic & Self-Adapting, Complex system, Connectivity, Dynamic environment, Enormous scale, Everything as a service, Heterogeneity, Integrated into Information Network, Intelligence, Interconnectivity, Interoperable Communication Protocols, Large scale, Limited energy, handles massive amount of data, Pervasive, Safety, Self-Configuring, sensing, considerations (Size, Space, Time) and Unique Identity. Figure 1 depicts the main essential characteristics of IoT.

Figure 1: Chief Characteristics of Internet of Things (IoT)

1.2 Reimbursements by Exploitation of Internet of Things:

By unlocking the massive potential of IoT, the following benefits of technology growth is attained create innovative services, improved performance, lowering time-to-market, efforts and probability of failure, manages billions of connected things, new revenue stream, quick time to market, reduce operation overhead, reduced costs – low start-up costs, reusable assets, scales as business grows.

1.3 Utilities of Internet of Things:

Sebastian and Ray, (2015a), lists the Utilities of IoT as Context-awareness, Dynamic and self-adapting, Integrated into information network, Intelligent decision-making capability, Interoperable communication protocols, Self-configuring, Unique identity.

The IoT technology can be broadly divided into system oriented or people oriented. Based on the applications there are several types like IoT Drones, Social IoT, IoT Analytics, Health care IoT etc., The scope is confined to the H-IoT (Health Care IoT).

According to Frost & Sullivan analysis, the global IoMT market is \$72.02 billion in 2021, with a compound annual growth rate of 26.2%. The IoMT market comprises of smart devices, such as habiliments and medical/vital monitors, sternly for health care use on the body, in the home, or in community, clinic or hospital settings; and linked real-time location, tele health and other services.

2. Health Care Internet of Things (H- Iot) - A Quick Review:

IoMT (Internet of Medical Things) is the unification of data from various medical gadgets (equipped with sensors) and software applications in the Health Care systems wirelessly. The IoMT collects remote patient health data from the wearable sensors; pre-processes the collected data, streams it to the Health Care Professionals via machine-to-machine (M to M) fortified with Wi-Fi. The Health Care data is stockpiled in the Cloud server for additional analysis. This data unification results in improved patient outcomes by combining the people, data and processes through connected medical devices and mobile applications. The IoMT thus increases the efficacy of Health Care devices, and the speed and accessibility of Health Care services.

2.1 Definition - IoMT:

Tech Target which gives the technology professionals and executives the information they need defines Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) as, “The Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) is the collection of medical devices and applications that connect to Health Care IT systems through online computer networks. Medical devices equipped with Wi-Fi allow the machine-to-machine communication that is the basis of IoMT. IoMT devices link to Cloud platforms such as Amazon Web Services, on which captured data can be stored and analyzed. IoMT is also known as Health Care IoT.”

2.2 Purposes for Acceptance of IoMT:

Gus Vlahos (2020) lists the rationale for IoMT adoption as it aids in remote medical support and care; improves and accelerates the clinician workflows; empowers good connectivity and helps to proactively conserve Good Health.

3. Research Gaps of IoMT:

- IoMT, deals with enormous amount (volume), of heterogenous Health Care data (variety), generated continuously (velocity); which, mandate’s the necessity to devise special techniques to tackle the big Health Care data.
- High cost is incurred on patients
- Health Care data includes extremely sensitive data which necessitates for devising strong privacy protection mechanisms.

- As all the data collected from the various sensors are stored in cloud one can understand the inescapability of cloud based IoT.
- IoMT implementation brings to the forefront issues like security perils, IoT Forensics.

4. IoT Forensics:

IoT forensics is a branch of digital forensics that carries out digital forensics in the IoT environment. The IoT forensics differs from the Digital Forensics in terms of evidence source which is vast, including traffic lights In-Vehicle Infotainment (IVI) systems, traffic lights, toddler or patient monitoring systems, and even medical implants in human and animals. The IoT security and forensics tools are in high demand [H. Chi et al., (2018)].

Chernyshev et al. [2018] mostly paid attention to the conceptual digital forensic models that are applied in an IoT environment. Bréda et al. [2018] examined the trifling functional forensic necessities of IoT devices to offer steadfast information. The forensic necessities like the user data fortification class by the access control policy, the access control functions, the data authentication, and integrity necessities of the stored data to preserve a least level of data integrity in the IoT environment. Losavio et al. [2018] scrutinized in minute detail the legal concerns on data collection and analysis in IoT forensics. There are also some surveys investigating IoT forensics in different IoT applications.

4.1 Significance of IoT Forensics:

Listing the significance of the IoT forensics (especially in health care) are as follows:

- Regulates and renovates the chain of events by examining the physical evidence and electronic data
- Applies analytical techniques to detect, excerpt, preserve, and analyze digital information
- Post-mortem investigation: detects discrepancies after the occurrence of events or when the system is inactive
- Case-centered: recreating a given illicit scenario
- Time-restricted process: post crime (notitia criminis)
- Forensics Readiness: keep everything ready for undertaking an investigation by complying with the forensics requirements, forensics standards; takes measurements to exploit the forensic value of the potential evidence, and curtail the number of resources consumed on the investigation
- Stipulate the judicial area and legal characteristics in service legal agreements concerning the forensics issues
- Still an infant branch Forensics.

Numerous authors [I. Sutherland, et al., (2014), D. Vandervort, et al., (2016), Z. A. Baig , et al.,(2017), N.-A. Le-Khac, et al., (2018), M. Stoyanova, et al., (2020)] concentrated on works related to forensic challenges related with health and fitness associated devices, automobiles, smart TVs, and smart cities, correspondingly.

5. Literature Review on IoT Forensics:

Many authors [Brotsis, S. et al.,(2019), Hossain, M. M. et al.,(2018), Ryu, J.H., ,et al.,(2019)]have studied the related features like the collection of Evidence from IoT devices and the interactions between the different actors (e.g. through privacy-preserving identity management techniques) .

Le, D. P. et al.,(2018) emphasized that the obligatory requirements are proper identity management and privacy preservation . Le, D.P.,,et al.,(2018), pointed about the immaturity of current solutions .Li, S., ,et al.,(2019),proposed a framework for evidence storage and scrutiny based on structured data logs, warranting the provenance and auditability of each evidence element.

5.1 New Models and Frameworks:

Sundresan Perumal, et al., (2015) proposed, a Last-on-Scene (LoS) algorithm, that is made of seven steps for things-of-interest identification; extending the ideas from NXP (2016). The digital forensic procedure is somewhat transformed and has seven steps. An online management platform that brings about and clusters IoT digital forensic cases, are also proposed. But it does not ensure elaboration of platform general specifications.

The proactive process is analogous to the preparation phase of other models and frameworks. IoT forensics is the similar as in Shams Zawoad, et al., (2015)]. Victor R. KEBANDE, et al., (2016) proposed framework complies with ISO/IEC 27043:2015, the international standard for incident investigation principles and processes. NXP (2016) proposed approaches to address challenges. Authors proposed a zone-based method for imminent IoT linked investigations. Ana Nieto, et al., (2017) IoT digital forensic investigation model splits IoT into a number of zones and it comprises of base device identification, a location finder represented by zones. But it is not implemented. Ana Nieto, et al., (2017), proposed the Privacy protection in IoT forensics. The Privacy aware IoT forensics model (Profit) includes the privacy requirements established by the ISO/IEC 29100:2011 privacy framework and is based on a preparatory phase. Profit was combined (2017)] with Digital witness [Ana Nieto , et al., (2016)] to advance IoT forensics while as long as user control of private data in [Nieto, A., et al., (2018)].

Tanveer Zia, et al., (2017) projected the adding of application specific forensics to the digital forensics model. This application precise component feeds data into the digital forensics' component of their model. It

offers relevant data for the IoT application in question. That permits focused mining of artifacts pertinent to the investigation.

5.2 Preparation Step with Repository:

In IoT, due to the nonexistence of logging and local data preservation, a type of pre-prepared local data repository of probable evidence appears to be the furthestmost warranted.

Oriwoh, E., et al., (2013 a,b) proposed a perception that presents a device in flanked by the local IoT network and the home firewall (Internet/Cloud) . The device offers standard security services like IDS/IPS, network monitoring, logging and threshold establishment.

S. Zawoad, et al., (2015) designed a edifice a Forensic Aware Ecosystem for IoT as a Forensics-aware IoT (FAIoT) model for backing up of consistent forensics inquiries in the IoT environment. The FAIoT has three parts: a secure evidence preservation module, a secure provenance module, and access to evidence through an API. Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) is the centralized trusted evidence repository as a new service to handle very large datasets. To ensure a proper chain of custody by conserving the access past of that evidence, a provenance aware file system [Kiran-Kumar Muniswamy-Reddy, et al.,(2006)] for the storehouse is projected. FAIoT is good at IoT forensics investigation but it is yet to be a practically usable system.

Meffert, C, et. al., (2017) contends that gathering of IoT devices permits an investigator to produce a clear picture of the events that have occurred. A centralized controller (reads and logs (with time stamps in secure storage with hashes for integrity) the state and cannot change it) is linked to devices, controllers (hubs) and the cloud to get IoT states. Open HAB, open source IoT device controller, is used to offer a proof-of-concept.

QiWang, et. al., (2017), proposed system warrants data provenance. It warrants to establish origin of data (at piece level), the processes and methodology by which it was formed. It aids an all-inclusive elucidation of the system activities (like the sequence, causal relationships etc.), together with malicious behaviors.

5.3 Real-World Systems:

The paper “Digital forensic approaches for Amazon Alexa ecosystem” [Hyunji Chung,et al.,(2017)] deliberates practical issues involved in the forensic analysis of IoT systems present in many households. The combo of cloud-native forensics with forensics of cohort devices, is the client-side forensics. The data of Alexa (cloud-based assistant), is in the cloud. A CIFT (Cloud-based IoT Forensic Toolkit) created is used to automate the process of data collection, visualization and evaluation.

In [Rahman, K. S,et al.,(2017)] the authors inspect and find out what data can be garnered in IoT attacks and what can be rebuilt from that data. The data are collected from hub and sensors (“sen.se” & Samsung hub of the home environment) and analyzed.

6. Internet of Things Forensics Challenges:

The main forensics challenges met in IoT environments are as follows:

- Analysis
- Anti-forensics Data Pooling
- Big IoT data analysis
- Cloud Forensics
- Complexity and Diversity of IoT
- Cyber security
- Data ownership
- Heterogeneity
- Individual privacy throughout digital investigations
- Interoperability
- IoT Forensic Readiness
- IoT Forensics Procedures/ Process
- Lack of Forensics Tools
- Legal liability
- Limitations of IoT Devices’ Storage
- Management and automation
- Multi-jurisdictions
- Power Consumption
- Intrusiveness
- Design Automation Challenges
- Multiple locations and networks
- Standardization, and Regulation
- Networks
- Interfaces and Human Factor Engineering
- Privacy

- Scale
- Securing the Chain of Custody
- Security Issues
- Sensors
- Shutting the devices down
- Survival period and visibility of the evidences

6.1 Internet of Things Forensics for Healthcare:

Healthcare sector is highly vulnerable to most important security attacks, owing to the confluence with many applications, heterogeneity, fragmentation and expanded attack surface [H. Abie (2019)]; and this gives rise to series of some new concerns about protection and security of users' medical data .

Akatyev, N. et al., (2017) gave an example of the Fitness trackers which is hacked for illicit financial gains, like marketing it to insurance companies or forcing the owner of the compromised device. The swelling number of medical identity theft cases is not astonishing, given the high value of medical data. Global Market Insights (2019) shows that the market size of mHealth applications and services is appreciated over \$86.4 billion in 2018, and is predicted to observe more than 29.6% compound annual growth from 2019 to 2025.

Wearables offer a large amount of forensics data and stand as a "digital witness" role [N. Akatyev, et al., (2019)]; which is used to repudiate the wrong evidence of a suspect or to trace the actions of the victim, near the time of the incident.

I. Gartner (2018) makes a mention of the rising popularity and sales (in 2019 sale reached 225 million) of the global wearable technology (smart watches) sales for 2019 will reach 225 million. Emphasis is to be made on the privacy-related issues, since the data gathered could be extremely sensitive. The swelling number of security and privacy events only highpoints the necessity for innovative, multi-faceted approaches powerful digital forensics methodology [S. Watson, et al.,(2016)]. Several mechanisms and the relevant concepts of preserving privacy are existing in literatures [Indumathi 2012, 2013 (a, b, c), 2020, 2021; Indumathi and Uma 2007(a, b), 2008(a, b, c, d)].

7. IoMT Forensics:

IoT includes the study of IoT devices, their systems and interrelations between different parts of their ecosystems. IoT forensics is a branch of digital forensics which deals with IoT linked crimes and consists of examination of the linked devices, the sensors and the cloud of data. IoMT is a sub branch of IoT and it deals with the medical devices and health care related crimes and it demands the examination of the relevant devices. IoMT forensics, an umbrella term, casing issues of IoMT and digital forensics, may support in investigating IoMT ecosystems and quickly respond to and report IoMT security incidents.

7.1 Research Gaps in IoMT Forensics:

Several authors [Harbawi, M., et al., (2017)]; Conti, M. et al., (2018), Stoyanova, M., et al.,(2020)] have divided the challenging forensics aspects into six groups: identification, collection, preservation, analysis and correlation, attack attribution, and finally, evidence presentation.

Evidence Identification:

- Yakubu, et al.,(2016), says that many examiners aren't aware of where, how, and when the investigated data is stored. For the Search and seizure used in scrutiny, yet research is to be made in the perspective of reliable tools to gather remaining evidences from the IoMT devices. The other open areas are as follows:
- Scope of the compromise and crime scene reconstruction (Conti, M., et al.,(2018) has stated that the real-time, autonomous dealings amongst several nodes, immensely lively nature of the communication hampers the recreation of the crime scene and to categorize the prospect of the harm.
- Device and data proliferation (due to the increase in volume, variety and velocity)
- Data Location (heterogenous devices, store various data formats in various geo-locations/data centres)
- Device type (various types of devices with various architecture, hard to detect due to lack of battery life or because they could not be distinguished from traditional household appliances)

Evidence Acquisition:

Lack of proper guidance or standardized method for evidence gathering from an IoT device in a forensically sound manner and produce it in Court [R. Mckemmish, (2008)]. One has to ensure a proper Chain of Custody. At times a small error in this step could make evidence material worthless and disturb the whole investigation process. H. Arshad, et al., (2018)] study of 100 random Digital Forensics lawsuits showed that in 8 out of 100 cases, there was an error or contamination during the evidence collection step. The other open areas are as follows:

- Lack of Training and Weak Knowledge Management
- Data Encryption (CSP has to get the decryption key from the user; trade-off between the process of investigation and privacy rights)

- Heterogeneous software and/or hardware specifications (users /investigators should have vast skill and knowledge of standards and hardware)
- Privacy and ethical considerations by accessing personal data
- Forensic value of evidence
- Lack of a common forensic model in IoT

Evidence Preservation and Protection:

Even with a single evidence it is difficult to manage the preservation and protection. The other open areas are as follows:

- **Securing the Chain of Custody:**

The term “Chain of Custody” is an accurate auditing control of original evidence material [J. Cosic and G. Cosic(2012)]. It is collection of evidence from the crime scene, preserving, analysing and presenting it in the court of law without any modification. In IoT Forensics, evidence data is collected from various remote servers, thereby raising the concern on maintaining proper Chain of Custody [S. O’Shaughnessy et al., (2013)]. The data collected by the IoT device, is subject to the analytic algorithms [S. Alabdulsalam, et al., (2018)] and the data is stored in the cloud in a different format; and it has to be reverted by analysis to the original format before submitting in the Court.

The Digital Chain of Custody (DCoC), uses the blockchain technology to protect the unstable nature of the digital evidence in a highly decentralized environment. Others propose to go beyond the well-known DCoC concepts and use technical devices that take the role of a human witness. The “digital witnesses” are technical devices that are supposed to manage digital electronic evidence from both technological and legal perspective [A. Nieto, et al.,(2016)].

- **Lifespan limitation:**

IoT devices have limited memory space; wherein, due to the 24*7 operation, data is overwritten, and the chance of missing evidence is more [I. Yaqoob et al.,(2019)]. Even the data transfer to a local storage device is not able to retain the Chain of evidence, as the data could have been altered during the transfer [I. Yaqoob et al.,(2019)]. Another issue is the employment of Real-Time Operating Systems (RTOS) by IoT devices which do not store data by default [C. Meffert, et al.,(2017)].

- **The Cloud Forensic Problem(s):**

Cloud Computing incorporates numerous technologies (like databases, load balancing, memory, networks, operating systems, resource scheduling, transaction management, virtualization, etc.,) which impose vulnerabilities on the cloud security and privacy. The data preserved is of little value. The Cloud Security Alliance (CSA), survey (117) recognized the top twelve intimidations to cloud computing as Abuse and nefarious use of cloud services; Account hijacking; Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs); Data breaches; Data loss; Denial of service; Insecure APIs; Insufficient Due Diligence; Malicious insiders; Shared technology vulnerabilities; System and application vulnerabilities; Weak identity, credential and access management.

The “Cloud forensic problem” is yet to be resolved. The mirroring of the Digital evidence in numerous places, or previously hashed and indexed, which makes the gathering of artefacts possible [L. Caviglione et al.,(2017)].

- **Securing Evidence depending on the Deployment and/or the Service model of the Cloud (PaaS, SaaS, IaaS):**

Fetching an evidence in SaaS and PaaS involves the service providers. The IaaS forensics investigators are to deal with both service providers and clients [A. Alenezi, et al.,(2019)]. Therefore, inspecting data of an IaaS user may need less limitations, whereas in the case of SaaS the access evidence information is either minimal or completely missing [J. Cosic and G. Cosic (2012)].

- **Data Protection and Lack of Transparency in Cloud Services:**

The data storage and data protection are taken care by the IaaS vendor. Owing to the availability of wide choice of vendors by the cloud users, data security is partially taken care. The next issue is the lack of transparency concerning the internal infrastructure of the cloud [[S. O’Shaughnessy et al.,(2013)]]]. The physical equipment of the CSP is geographically distributed across the globe paving way for the challenge of various governance of laws of several countries.

- **Data Storage Period in the Cloud:**

The duration depends upon the service provider. Different countries have various Legislation on how to store data and for how long [EU countries (6 months based on GDPR), US (6 months to one year). Certain stakeholders like suppliers have no legal provision for a minimum or maximum storage period, obviously forming preconditions for promising crimes.

Evidence Analysis and Correlation:

The technical challenges like metadata from IoT nodes lacks many items like temporal information (provenance of end-to-end analysis of residual evidences of modified, accessed and created time etc.), correlation of the voluminous heterogeneous data gathered from different IoT devices through IoT sensors as evidences contain inborn personal information leading to privacy violation. The other open areas are as follows:

End-to-End Analysis:

The continuous stream of voluminous big data comes from the IoT nodes and this causes the end-to-end analysis of the current information surpassing the capabilities of a single investigator or an investigating team.

- **Data Provenance:**

Data provenance gives examiners information about proprietorship and alteration history of data objects. IoT Forensics offers very little certainty about the data origin, individual who or what formed and/or altered the data object. The degree of clarification of the data origin, is based on the cloud model [S. O'Shaughnessy et al., (2013)] or the preparedness of the vendor to co-operate with the establishments.

- **Time Lining and Limited Correlation of Evidence:**

It is impossible to virtually link and obtain logical homogeneity of evidence, collected from manifold IoT nodes; as many IoT devices do not store any metadata (e.g. time and geospatial information, copyright information, creation and last modification date). This virtually makes the link and logical uniformity of evidence, collected from multiple IoT nodes, nearly impossible. D. Lillis, et al., (2016) pointed the unified time lining problem. Conti, M., et al., (2018), states that lack of temporal information, forces the investigators to guess the causal links.

- **Legal Issues:**

Losavio et al. [2018], in their paper mentioned about the issue of cross-border crimes, lack of transparent procedural and contractual agreements. Even a single file is split into data blocks and stored across diverse jurisdictions; which might lead to a breach of the law in the state where the forensic practice is really carried out. The dispersed international geographical locations, have their own regulations, encouragingly surges the amount of time, the cost and the exertion related with a certain investigation [N. Rana, et al.,(2017)].

Attack and Deficit Attribution:

Even if an evidence points out specifically to an exact IoT node as the cause of the crime, there is no guarantee that it will direct the investigators to the criminals. The other open areas are as follows:

- **Lack of User Information / IP Anonymity:**

Authors [N. Rana, et al.,(2017); D. Lillis,et al.,(2016)]have recorded that the acceptance of IP obscurity tools, user-friendly policies and the need for nominal information offered by cloud service providers, impedes the tracking down of an illicit very problematic.

- **Sharing Resources and Identifying Liabilities:**

In the modern informational infrastructure multiple users simultaneously share a physical server which will have many virtual machines used by several people at the same time [S. Alabdulsalam, et al.,(2018)]. It is difficult to just fix and establish the exact user who has done the illegal activity. Investigators will have to examine not only the services used by a single customer, but a multi-tenant infrastructure, extensive sharing of resources and multiple potentially vulnerable interfaces[S. O'Shaughnessy and A. Keane(2013)].Correctly detecting and confirming the link between digital and physical identity with correct assumptions could extremely predisposition the investigation process[F. Servida and E. Casey(2019)].The presence of indication events (e.g. motion detection or door opening) is unable to expose the criminals identity. [F. Servida and E. Casey (2019)].

Lastly, there is no guarantee for the accurate device location and time settings from the geolocation information mined from a certain IoT device and no way to determine if the device was also used by one more person at the equivalent time [F. Servida and E. Casey(2019)].The concept of BYOD allowed for work by the employees, makes the chore of detecting accountabilities even harder [N. Rana, et al.,(2017)].

Evidence Presentation:

S. Zawoad et al.,(2015) said that presenting the discoveries of an IoT-centric case stances some new challenges like want of elementary understanding of cloud computing and forensics, or explain the intricate technicalities behindhand such a multifaceted architecture in the very inadequate time of the trial. R. C. Hegarty et al. [2014] says that the information accretion and processing using diagnostic functions, could affect the structure of the data and modify its meaning [Adjei, O.,,et al.,(2018)]. The reverse engineering of data structure by the forensics practitioners [D. Quick,et al.,(2018)]demands the necessity of advanced presentation techniques.

8. Conclusion:

This research work highlighted the recent trends in the H-IoF domain by surveying the recently proffered applications, models, protocols, and methods implied in securing the DF investigation process. The research findings on DF investigation process risks in IoT emphasize the leeway of the challenges like threats, vulnerabilities. Inquiries of contemporary research models show that common of DF solutions are incapable of adopting to the changing scenario. Integration of technologies like digital twin, deep learning, artificial intelligence-based fuzzy logic methods, elliptical cryptographic algorithms, and block chain can be used to aid in firming the security of the digital artifacts. On the negative side, it has augmented the intricacy factor of the entire system. Because of the high level of abstraction of such multifaceted solutions, the transparency in the

intent of digital forensics artifacts has declined. In this work, exertions have been made to report the progression of existing H-LoF technologies, persistent efforts that are being made by the scientific researchers internationally in predecessor discussed topics. Still, there is always a opportunity of examination.

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